

USE OF QUALITY ENGLISH READERS AND LITERATURE TEXTS AS A PANACEA FOR LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIAN EARLY CHILDREN

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Abstract

Many scholars have investigated the persistent poor performance of Nigerian students in English, particularly at the secondary and tertiary levels. However, little attention has been paid to foundational factors at the early stage of language development. Therefore, this study was designed to investigate two critical issues: (1) the use of non-complaint English Readers and Literature texts in primary schools and (2) the widespread violation of Nigeria's language policy, which recommends initial literacy development in the mother tongue before the introduction of English in selected public and private primary schools in Ondo West Local government. Cummins' interdependence hypothesis and Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory, which both emphasize the centrality of a strong first language foundation for effective second language acquisition and cognitive development, served as the framework. Adopting a qualitative approach through policy analysis and classroom-based evidence, this study argues that premature immersion in English and reliance on inappropriate instructional materials disrupt the transfer of linguistic and cognitive skills from the first to the second language. This weakens the overall language competence of learners and contributes to sustained academic underperformance. The findings reveal a significant gap between policy prescriptions and pedagogical practices in Nigerian primary schools. This study concludes that this trend can be reversed by the effective implementation of mother- or tongue-based instruction and the strict regulation of instructional materials to foster bilingual competence and improve the performance of students in English. Therefore, this study recommends renewed policy enforcement, teacher training, and stakeholder awareness as critical steps toward addressing the root causes of the problem.

Introduction

The geographical expression known as Nigeria today consists of over 400 ethnic nationalities. It came under the British colonial rule, and English became the official language of administration. English was consequently inherited or adopted by the succeeding administration after the colonialists' exit in 1960. The country witnessed an all-round development before and a few years after independence. One of the reasons for this is that Nigerians who had the opportunity to have formal education had a solid grasp of English and, by extension, good education. By 1966, the country witnessed two military coups that have been described as ethnically motivated.

In fact, the counter-military coup of July 29, 1966, witnessed the mass killing of officers and soldiers of the Eastern Region across Nigeria Army Barracks. Retardation in all spheres of our national life began to set in 1966. Since then, Nigeria has been grappling with the problem of development as the country seems to be bedeviled by the problem of leadership.

Although successive governments have tried to make an impact in various sectors, their efforts have not yielded desirable results owing to several factors, such as poor policy implementation and lack of competent personnel. As noted earlier, Nigeria adopted English as the language of its colonial masters as the official language and medium of instruction in Nigerian schools. However, English language learning and mastery in Nigeria is currently in a precarious situation, and this should be a cause for concern for all, considering the immense contributions of language to the development of various sectors in Nigeria. How else can one express one's thoughts or ideas other than through language? In recent years, some graduates of tertiary institutions in Nigeria cannot communicate effectively in English. It has even reached a level where some graduates cannot construct two correct sentences. This problem could be attributed to the child's feeble education foundation while in the primary school. It is like erecting a house on sand; it will not stand the test of time. It will sooner than later collapse. According to the history of Nigeria and her political experience, English has come to stay in Nigeria, not only as the official language but also as the medium of instruction in Nigerian schools. As observed by Adegoke (2009), English is the only language that unifies the over 450 ethnic groups in Nigeria. He claims English is a 'garb' one must wear because of the nation's important position.

The study focuses on early childhood children at the primary school level. This is because the researcher believes that is the foundation level. If the foundation of the country's education is well-laid at the primary level, then one can be sure of producing good and functional graduates soon. This position is aptly captured in the analogy given by Giordano Bruno cited in (Onukaogu 2010) while trying to emphasize the importance of reading:

If the first button of a man's coat is wrongly buttoned, all the rest are certain to be crooked. Reading is the first button in the garment of education.

The researcher also believes that the education of the early child is like the first button of a man's coat, which must not be wrongly buttoned otherwise, the rest of the buttons are surely going to be crooked. In this study, the researcher focuses on the English readers or texts used at the primary school level. The researcher is interested in the type of books and children's literature used. Do these books stimulate children's interest? Do they develop language and stimulate thinking? Are the texts and literature materials appropriate for the recommended class? How systematic are the topics? Do the books contain illustrations that illustrate the topic taught?

Literature Review

Place of Indigenous Languages in Nigeria's Educational System

Many scholars have advocated the need to prioritize the development of indigenous languages instead of dissipating so much energy on the development and learning of English, which is the language of the colonizers. The proponents of this position are quick to refer to some nations of the world, such as China,

Japan, and North and South Korea, who have developed even as they use local languages as the medium of instruction in schools. They believe that this can be replicated in Nigeria. As good as the opinion is, some of us feel that the Nigeria question may never allow this to succeed. The country's heterogeneity will make it impossible to impose one of the indigenous languages. Furthermore, none of the three major ethnic groups (Hausa, Igbo, and Yoruba) is prepared to adopt the other language as its lingua franca. This is an ego problem, and none of these major ethnic groups would want their egos to be bruised.

Moreover, post-independence Nigerian leaders, particularly from 1966 until now, conducted themselves as ethnic chauvinists. Appointments into key ministerial positions are based on ethnic considerations, and many policies emanating from these departments are not of national interest. The heads of many of these key Ministries and Parastatals brazenly appropriate where they head for people of their ethnic nationalities. This attitude deepens suspicions among various ethnic nationalities, particularly among the major ethnic groups. This is a major stumbling block to the adoption of one of these languages as a medium of instruction in Nigerian schools. Each ethnic group does not want to lose its identity. Each group wants to preserve its language and culture and does not want to be dominated by the ethnic group whose language may be adopted. These are the reasons why English, which is a neutral and international language, shall continue to be relevant in Nigeria.

Policy Statement on the Use of English and Indigenous Languages in Nigeria

The government of Nigeria has made pronouncements on languages in Nigeria as contained in the National Policy on Education (1998 and 2004). The pronouncements are as follows:

NPE (1998) Section 2 p. 8 (14c) reads "government shall ensure that the medium of instruction in pre-primary education is principally the mother tongue or the language of the immediate environment."

Section 2 p. 9 (8c) on NPE (2004) emphasized the mother tongue education policy as follows:

"the medium of instruction shall be the environment language for the first 3 years." During this period, English shall be taught as a subject".

The Nigerian language policy requires that every Nigerian child receives education in the mother tongue in the first 3 years of primary education. In addition, the child should learn another Nigerian language and French as a foreign language. Lawal (2005:15) noted that the policy has been very difficult to implement because of the educated class's attitude that their children speak English right from the infant class. Lawal added that other factors that made policy implementation difficult include the collapse of the public education system, which has compelled many parents to find more viable alternatives in fee-paying private schools where English is the language of classroom instruction and other activities. She noted that this is to the detriment of the government's language policy.

Lawal (2005) argued that the mother tongue policy cannot be faulted. She held that the mother tongue is an asset that children bring with them to school and can help them acquire literacy. When children learn to read in the mother tongue, they will be able to read in a second language situation as in English. She concluded that as parents ignorantly insulate their children from the mother tongue to induce facility in the use of the English language, the children are deprived of a basic source of education and imaginative development. Consequently, the children are neither competent in the basic grammar of English to be able to read and write well nor competent in the mother tongue to demonstrate basic literacy. These inadequacies are transferred to secondary schools and tertiary institutions.

Despite the government's pronouncement on the use of English and mother tongue as contained in the National Policy on Education, it is saddening that English is in a pathetic state in Nigeria today. Equally disturbing is that in spite of the provisions that the mother tongue is used as a medium of instruction in the lower primary school, private operators of primary education do not comply with the policy. The advantage of training pupils using the mother tongue at junior primary and senior primary schools has been demonstrated through empirical

studies, such as the six-year Yoruba Medium Project (Fafunwa et al. 1975), which demonstrates that full six-year primary education in the mother tongue with English taught as a subject was not only viable but also gave better results than all English schooling. Today, the mother tongue education policy has been discarded in private schools, which are now being patronized mainly by the elites. For many years now, even the low public primary schools have had bouts of strikes that have eroded the confidence of parents in public primary schools. Consequently, a large percentage of children in a second language situation are forced to learn and acquire two languages at a time. At home, they use their mother tongue, and in school, they use English. The effect of this is that the children acquire only a small amount of the two languages. Their knowledge of the two languages is shallow. This position is further buttressed by the behaviorist Theorist using the Stimulus-Response Theory. Machado (1999) succinctly affirmed that

as parents and main caregivers reward, correct, ignore, or punish the young child's communication, they exert considerable influence over both the quantity and quality of language usage and the child's communication attitude. The child's utterances may grow, seem to stand still, or become unified depending on the feedback from others.

This theory is attributed to the work of B. F. Skinner, a pioneering researcher in the field of learning theory. Language development is described as a process that begins early in life, when a person begins to acquire language by mimicking it and learning it as it is spoken. It is an impression that treats development in relation to language on the basis of language acquisition in infants. The requirements for language development are biological, environmental, social, and linguistic factors. Phonological development, semantic development, grammatical development, and pragmatic development also exist.

From the above, one can rightly assert that failure to allow the children's language to develop by means of using the mother tongue as the medium of instruction in pre-primary and junior primary schools as provided for in the National Policy on Education in the long run inhibits the mastery of English by the pupils. Adequate knowledge of the mother tongue enhances effective learning and acquisition of English. However, it is disheartening that Nigerian children at pre-primary and junior primary schools are not allowed to have a sound footing in their mother tongue. He is put at the mercy of authors who unleash a deluge of English readers and children's literature on him. This is the focus of this study.

Empirical Studies on Mother Tongue and English Language Performance in Nigeria

Recent empirical studies within the Nigerian context have continued to highlight the critical role of the mother tongue in the acquisition and performance of ESL. For instance, Adams et al. (2024) found a statistically significant relationship between mother tongue instruction and the academic achievement of students in the English language, with the instructional approach accounting for a substantial proportion of the variance in the performance of learners. Similarly, Amaechi and Ohakamma (2024) demonstrated that learners who possess a strong foundation in their indigenous language tend to exhibit higher proficiency in English, thereby reinforcing the interdependence between the development of first and second languages.

Corroborating these findings, Humble et al. (2024) provided empirical evidence from primary schools in Nigeria, showing that reading skills acquired in the mother tongue can be effectively transferred to English, thus validating the principle of cross-linguistics transfer. This aligns with Ochagu and Agban (2022), who identified mother tongue factors as significant determinants of English language use and competence among learners.

However, other studies reveal a more complex picture. Uwena and Okfar (2025) report a growing preference for English among Nigerian school children driven by socio-cultural and institutional pressures, often at the expense of MLD. This trend is further compounded by the systematic challenges in policy implementation. Nyitse and Dzer (2024) observed that actual classroom practices frequently deviate due to a lack of materials, teacher preparedness, and institutional support despite policy provisions supporting mother tongue instruction.

In addition, Akinlabi (2021) highlighted the phenomenon of mother tongue interference, noting that inadequate mastery of both the first language and English can result in linguistics transfer errors that negatively affect academic performance.

From the empirical studies above, it is observed that the works of Adams et al. (2024), Amaechi and Ohakama (2024), Humble et al. (2024), and Ochagu and Agban (2022) are related to the present study as they all examine the need for strong foundation in the mother tongue as a necessary prelude to a good performance in English language acquisition/learning. However, they differ in focus. This study's major focus is examining the English Readers and Literature texts used for teaching Nigerian children to determine their suitability. The missing link is that none of the abovementioned studies has worked on the quality of English readers and literature text as a panacea to language development in the Nigerian Early Child.

More broadly, recent policy-oriented research indicates that adherence to Nigeria's language of instruction remains low, particularly in private and urban schools, thereby undermining literacy development at the foundational level.

Taken together, these studies suggest that while the mother tongue has significant potential to enhance English language acquisition, its effectiveness is contingent upon proper implementation, appropriate instructional materials, and alignment with educational policy. This study builds on this body of research by specifically interrogating the role of instructional materials that address non-curriculum complaints and the systematic neglect of mother tongue instruction at the foundational stage of learning.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on theoretical perspectives that emphasize the role of the first language in the acquisition of a second language and overall cognitive development. Specifically, the study draws on Cummins' interdependence hypothesis and Vygotsky's Social-Cultural Theory, situated within the broader framework of MTB-MLE. These theories provide a robust explanation for the importance of early linguistic experience in chasing learners' academic outcomes.

Mother Tongue-Based Education

Mother Tongue-Based Education advocates that a child's first language should serve as a medium of instruction in the early years of schooling. This approach is grounded in the understanding that children learn best when instruction begins in a familiar linguistic and cultural context. According to UNESCO (2003), the use of the mother tongue enhances comprehension, participation, and cognitive development, thereby providing a strong foundation for subsequent learning. In Nigeria, the National Policy on Education recommends the use of the mother tongue or language of the immediate environment in early education. However, this policy's widespread neglect undermines effective language development and contributes to learning difficulties.

Cummins' Interdependence Hypothesis

(Cummins, 1979, 2000) posits that proficiency in a second language (L2) is dependent on the level of competence already attained in the first language (L1). According to their theory, a common underlying proficiency supports the transfer of cognitive and linguistic skills across languages. Skills developed in the mother tongue, such as reading comprehension and critical thinking problem-solving, can be transferred to the second language, provided adequate exposure and support. This theory is particularly relevant to the present study because it explains how weak foundation in the mother tongue caused by early and excessive exposure to English can negatively affect learners' ability to effectively acquire English. When pupils are prematurely immersed in English without sufficient MT or L1 grounding, the transfer of skills is disrupted, leading to poor language proficiency and academic underachievement.

Vygotsky's Socio-cultural Theory

Vygotsky's Socio-Cultural Theory (1978) emphasizes the fundamental role of socio-linguistic interaction in cognitive deployment. Central to this theory is the concept of the ZPD, which highlights the difference between

what a learner can achieve independently and what can be achieved with guidance. In this context, language series serves as a primary tool for thought, learning, and meaning making.

Vygotsky argues that learning is most effective when it occurs within a familiar cultural and linguistic environment. Therefore, introducing formal education in a language that the learner does not understand can inhibit cognitive development and limit meaningful classroom interaction. In relation to this study, the premature use of English as a medium of instruction coupled with inappropriate reading materials constrains the learners' ability to actively participate in the learning process, thereby affecting their overall academic performance.

Relevance of Theories to the Study

The integration of theories of interdependence and socio-cultural theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the consequences of neglecting mother tongue instruction in early education. Cummins explained the cognitive and linguistic transfer between languages, whereas Vygotsky highlighted the importance of social context and meaningful interaction in learning. These theories underscore the need for a solid foundation in the mother tongue as a prerequisite for effective language learning. Therefore, the study situates the problem of poor English performance within these theoretical perspectives, arguing that the use of non-complaint instructional materials and violation of language policy disrupt cognitive development and language transfer processes. Addressing these issues requires not only policy enforcement but also a pedagogical shift that recognizes the critical roles of the first language.

Methodology

Research design

The researcher conducted this study by visiting 10 private and 10 public primary schools in the Ondo West Local Government. He asked the English language teachers questions on English texts and literature that they use in teaching and learning English. In all the private nursery primary schools visited, pupils are streamed into the following classes:

1. Kindergarten II
2. Kindergarten II
3. Nursery I
4. Nursery II
5. Primaries I-V

In public primary schools, the pupils' streaming is as follows:

1. Kindergarten I
2. Kindergarten II
3. Primaries I-VI

From above, it is observed that public primary schools do not operate Nursery I and II and private nursery and primary schools terminate their primary education in primary B. This does not conform with Nigeria's education system, which is 6-3-3-4.

Research Instrument

The research instruments used for collecting data for this study were as follows:

1. Oral questions from the English teachers
2. A questionnaire was used to elicit responses from the teachers of selected private and public primary schools visited for the study. The questionnaire is titled: Teachers' Perception of English Readers' and Literature's use in Selected Public and Private Primary Schools.
3. Examination/scrutiny of available English and Literature readers in schools to determine their compliance with the curriculum to draw findings and conclusions

The following are the oral questions posed to the forty English language teachers in the public and private nursery primary schools.

1. Does the pre-primary school have a curriculum?
2. Are there English readers and pre-primary school literature?
3. Are English readers and the literature curriculum complaint?
4. Does junior primary school have an English language curriculum?
5. Are there English readers and literature for primaries 1-3 which represent the junior primary?
6. Are the text contents in line with the curriculum requirements?
7. To what extent is the content of the readers and literature in senior primary (that is,. 4-5) In agreement with the curriculum ?
8. What does the national education policy say about mother tongue in pre-primary and junior primary schools?
9. How many English readers are recommended per class?
10. Why are English readers not uniform in schools?
11. How systematic are readers' topics treated?

TwelveHow suitable are the children's literature for the recommended classes?

In addition to the abovementioned questions, the researcher sought for and obtained modules (language curriculum) for primaries 1-6 and juxtaposed the content with the topics in the English readers to draw his findings.

The following information was gathered from the oral interview:

1. It was gathered that there is no curriculum for the nursery. The author just writes what they like.
2. English readers and literature for pre-primary students.
3. Since there is no pre-primary curriculum, it could not be said that the English readers and literature conform to the curriculum.
4. Junior primary school has language curriculum.
5. There are English readers for junior primary school students.
6. The teachers believed that the contents align with the curriculum requirements.
7. Some teachers believe that English readers largely conform to the curriculum.
8. Some teachers do not know what NPE says while some do.
9. The type of English readers varies among schools.

Ten the teachers replied that schools go for the type they want.

Apart from the information obtained from the teachers, the researcher also gathered the following:

- The English language is taught at the pre-primary level even when there is no English curriculum.
- Authors write English readers and children's literature based on their whims.

A review of many texts revealed that the topics treated are not systematic and, in any case, cannot assist the pupils in language development.

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION ON THE use OF ENGLISH READERS AND LITERATURE IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS = 40

English readers and literature use		Agree	%	Disagree	%
1	English readers and literature are curriculum complaints	18	45%	22	55%
2	Topics in English readers are systematically treated	15	37.5%	25	62.5%
3	English readers and literature are suitable for their classes.	18	45%	22	55%

4	The English readers will find exercises appropriate for the illustration	13	32.5%	27	67.5%
5	Readers and literature contain suitable illustrations and pictures	10	25%	30	75%
6	The proliferation of English readers and literature in pre-primary junior and senior primary schools is welcome.	20	50%	20	50%
7	The Ministry of Education only shall approve/recommended English readers and literature for all public and private schools.	22	55%	18	45%
8	School heads and owners have the right to choose English readers and literature	15	37.5%	25	62.5%
9	English should be used as a medium of instruction from the pre-primary level.	22	55%	18	45%
10	The mother tongue should be used to teach all subjects in junior primary school, except English as a subject.	15	37.5%	25	62.5%

From the responses of the 40 teachers sampled for this study, it can be concluded that most English readers and literature used in schools are grossly unsuitable for the Nigerian child.

Moreover, despite the policy statement that the mother tongue should be used to teach at the pre-primary and junior primary school levels, most teachers do not seem to see any rationale for this. Therefore 22 of the 40 respondents (55%) supported the use of English as a medium of instruction from the pre-primary level.

We also note from the responses that half of the respondents do not see any evil in the flood of the book market with all kinds of books. Most authors of these books treat the topics in such a haphazard manner that they cannot aid any language development in the Nigerian early child. In a nutshell, the picture painted from the responses is not encouraging.

Examination of the Contents of Available English Readers and Literature in Juxtaposition with Government-Approved Curriculum

Some texts or readers were ensampled. The first to be considered is an English reader entitled “Learn to Read BK.” 2” by “Lolade sola-Giwa. It is meant for pupils in nursery 2.

This text opens with the revision of the letters and then proceeds to the next topic, which is not only wrongly titled as “SPELL LEARN THE FOLLOWING WORDS” but also consists of incorrectly selected words. One wonders why, from the revision of alphabets, the immediate topic treated is 3-letter words, and immediately after this, there is a collection of seven sentences. The students are required to read the sentences. The pattern that pervades the English readers is from letter revision to 3-letter word spelling drill and then to reading of sentences. This is not a good way of imparting language skills to children. Another English reader is the Metropolitan English series. The text is entitled: Basic Reading Skills by Stella Agwuna for Primary 1. The English sounds that seem to be the focus of the text are haphazardly treated. The sounds are not systematically treated. The given examples are confusing. There are many strange pronunciation symbols that will confuse even English teachers. For example, on page 1 of the text title ‘Activity1’, there is referred to as a phonetic table and sound pronunciation, e.g.,

a = er, ae
g = ‘dai’ ‘g’
k = ker, ki, k’s, ke, kai
o = ou3’, ð’, b, ‘ð

r = a, rae

c = si c's

What we have at the right are what the author considers the pronunciations of the letters written before them. This is very misleading. One would expect the author to provide examples of words where the sounds are realized for better understanding. However, the abovementioned misleading topics are found in other places in the text. The topics treated in the text are not systematic.

In the same category as the text above is another text titled:

WORKING WITH SOUNDS PHONICS BOOKS 4 and 5 for primaries 4 and 5 pupils, respectively, does not organize the treatment of speech sounds in the text. The text content does not conform to the curriculum. English readers and literature of these sorts are commonly found in visited private primary schools. In public primary schools, there is a special scheme of work on English for kindergarten I and II pupils from 1st to 3rd term. However, there is no English reader based on the scheme of work with which pupils can interact under the guidance of teachers. The only English reader available is titled: **PLAYTIME WITH RHYMES** by Adjai Robinson and published by University Press Limited, Ibadan in 2007. Only the teachers have a copy of the book in the visited school.

Qualities that should be found in English readers and early childhood literature

Books selection is not an easy task for teachers. In Machado (1999), McCord (1995) highlights:

As caregivers or teachers, we have the responsibility of selecting each book with much thought to its content and relevance to particular children.

Also, Machado (1999) emphasized that careful consideration should be given to the selection of books that are appropriate for the child's age. Again, Machado (1999) extensively discussed the importance of PBs in early child education. She insisted that picture books are a vital step on the child's path to literacy and that they provide the opportunity to:

- Build a positive attitude toward books and reading.
- Develop language, stimulate thinking, and develop socially.
- Experience visual and esthetic variety.
- Develop real readers and writers

Lawal (2005) observed that children's literature books focus on two issues: (1) extra-literature matters such as illustration, physical construction, technical production-print, color, and binding; and (2) literary quality. She further explained that carefully written literature is one in which the writer must appreciate that it is a unique process of communicating thoughts, feelings, attitudes, and ideas to impressionable minds. She added that for literature to be worthwhile for children, writers must ensure that young readers share in the communication by receiving or understanding these experiences and ideas and responding to them. Then, the literature will be purposeful and functional. (Lawal, 2005)

However, it is heart-warming to note that not all English readers are bad. Some texts, for instance, the Macmillan new primary English, were found to have largely complied with the curriculum contents on English language teaching and learning in the primary education level. The topics in the text are well organized and as laid out in the English curriculum.

Findings

From the study, the low level of literacy among Nigerian children and even graduates of tertiary institutions is a product of the following:

- Proliferation of English Readers and Literature, most of which are useless for the early language development of children.
- Depriving the early child of a solid grasp of the mother tongue before English is introduced to him.

Conclusion

Although there are many factors militating against the effective teaching and learning of English, it seems that the most fundamental of these is the English readers that the early child will read after oral activity. The majority of the English readers and literature found in most primary schools are anything but useful for the early child. When the early child begins to read and does not have contact with the English readers whose content and topics are systematically treated as well as have contact with literature texts that are appropriate for the class and age for which they are written, the learning of English will be greatly impeded. That is the real cause of the illiteracy that confronts Nigeria as a nation today.

Recommendation

Therefore, English language teachers must ensure that they select quality English readers and literature for the early child. The situation of Nigerian children is aptly captured in a Yoruba people's proverb- "Amunkun eru ro wo. "O ni oke le n wo, e o wo isale" Translated: The lame is told that the load on his head is crooked. He replied that they only observed that the load was crooked at the top and never looked below. In other words, since the lower limbs are not straight, the load the lame is carrying is bound to be crooked. This is the Nigerian child's dilemma.

The government has a duty to compel both public and private primary schools to obey well-intentioned policies. The government should also compel all schools to patronize only approved English readers. This situation where all manners of authors unleash books that will not aid their English language learning must be discontinued. It is to the detriment of our children.

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